

How to set up on-farm crop trials testing microbial inoculants

Problem

There is increasing awareness of the environmentally harmful effects of artificial fertilizers used in crop production across Europe and beyond. On top of that, recent disruptions in global supply chains have led to dramatic increases in the price of manufactured fertilizers, making them less financially attractive to farmers. Growers are seeking more cost-effective and environmentally beneficial solutions to improve soil fertility, water and nutrient use efficiency, to ultimately build resilience through improving and maintaining quality of agricultural soils. Furthermore, the threat that climate change is posing to crop yield stability is increasing each year, with multiple abiotic and biotic stresses affecting crops with increasing frequency.

Solution

Microbial inoculants (MI) are soil amendments containing beneficial microorganisms, able to promote crop health and growth. A wide range of MI products are available commercially, presented as inputs for crop production that increase soil fertility and nutrient accessibility in crops. MI can be easily applied to soils, seeds and crop roots, and are cheaper than more resource-intensive inputs. Furthermore, the contents of MI are biological and free from chemical products, lowering their environmental impact in contrast to manufactured nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium fertilisers. The effects of MI on soil and crop health can vary depending on local environmental conditions and management. This means it is a good idea to test any products on-farm to determine if they will provide a benefit at a given location. Aimed at farmers, advisors and researchers thinking of carrying out their own on-farm trials testing MI, this practice abstract provides guidance to design trials that assess their impacts as a natural method to increase soil fertility, soil health and crop growth.

Benefits

On-farm trials testing MI will help to determine if they are an easier, cheaper, and more practical alternative to conventional inputs and application methods. Moreover, testing MI on commercial farms will contribute to research into their efficacy. In the SolACE project, a range of MI products were trialled on farms, including commercial products available to buy online directly from suppliers (Figure 2).

Applicability box

Theme

Microbial inoculants, crop production, nutrient use, crop nutrient efficiency, reduced fertilizer, abiotic stress

Agronomic conditions

All agronomic conditions

Application time

Sowing, crop establishment

Period of impact

Actual crop, Succeeding crop

Equipment

Adaptations to equipment may be required for application

Best in

Any crop system responding to climate and economic stressors

Figure 1 (top): soil sample taken from an on-farm trial in North-East England, trialing microbial inoculants [Source: LEAF, 2021]. Figure 2 (below): Smart Rotations commercial microbial inoculant used in on-farm trials [Source: PlantWorks, 2021].

Practical recommendation

To set up on-farm trials using MI, follow this step-by-step guide:

- Identify a crop you think will benefit from a microbial treatment. MI can be applied to any crops. Ideally a selected crop will be a regular part of a rotation subject to biotic (e.g., pest or disease) or abiotic (e.g. nutrient deficiency or drought) stressors.
- Select and buy a MI product you are interested in using on-farm. Make sure to check if the product is approved for commercial use in the specific location (country/region) and according to any relevant certification standards.
- Select two adjacent areas in a crop field that can be used for a control plot and a variable plot. Make sure that the two plots are similar in every other way, with the same past crop rotation, management and similar soil type, aspect, and slope. Keep away from field boundaries, hedges, and margins. Plot sizes can be as large as a hectare but must be at least 6m in length and the width of relevant planting equipment. This ensures a large enough area to avoid unwanted external influences on the area.
- At sowing, sow seeds in the control plot as 'normal' based on typical management and cropping system. In the inoculated plot, sow seeds (of the same variety) along with application of the MI as indicated. Record date and time of sowing and application, soil type, and seed rate. Keep seed rates the same in each plot and sow both plots on the same day.
- Keep all applications of inputs identical in each trial plot (e.g., fertilizer rate, irrigation level, etc.).
- Once the crop is established, record and compare any differences between the plots throughout the growing season (e.g., disease occurrence, leaf greenness, evidence of pests, crop height, etc.). At harvest, measure and compare yields in each plot.
- Where you only have two plots to compare, consider if any differences in yield you recorded have resulted in an economic benefit considering the costs of application and the value of the crop.
- If possible, it is a good idea to repeat your trial at several places within the field so that you can calculate average yields and the standard deviation of those yields; this will give you a better idea of whether the differences between the treatments are due to simple variability within the field, or if they are true differences.

Figure 3. Plot design for on-farm trial using a microbial inoculant with and without irrigation in two varieties of potatoes (Premier and Rooster).

Further information

Videos

- SolACE Stakeholder Workshop: Upscaling Knowledge from Bio-stimulant Experiments to the Farm

Weblinks

- SolACE – WP5 - Co-assessment of novel crop genotypes and management innovations in farmers networks

About this practice abstract and SolACE

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